

DIVERSITY OF PHYTOPLANKTON IN SARALA SAGAR RESERVOIR, WANAPARTHY DISTRICT, TELANGANA

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, phytoplankton belonging to 66 species under 45 genera was recorded from Sarala sagar reservoir, Wanaparthi district, Telangana during the period from April 2017 to March 2019. Sarala Sagar reservoir is located in Chinnavagu a tributary of the Krishna River about 21kms away from the district. Results revealed that, Cyanophyceae was found to be the dominant group of phytoplankton followed by Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae with and respectively. Sarala sagar reservoir is found to be rich in phytoplankton diversity and hence productive. Physico-chemical factors were found to be the important factors influencing the growth of phytoplankton. The lake is said to be moderately oligotrophic.

KEYWORDS: Diversity, Phytoplankton, Physico-chemical parameters, Saralasagar reservoir.

INTRODUCTION

Phytoplankton is a functional aquatic community based upon which the aquatic food web is culminating.^[1] Studies on physicochemical factors and phytoplankton standing crop of its habitat are essential for the proper management of water resources and for the prediction of the potential changes in the aquatic ecosystem.^[2,3,4] reported that phytoplankton populations are mostly structured by the physical and chemical variables of their environment. These factors have also been reported to be responsible for the heterogeneity in phytoplankton composition and biomass.^[5,6,7]

The present study has been carried out to know the diversity and distribution of phytoplankton in Sarala sagar reservoir of Wanaparthy district, Telangana. This study is relevant since the present water body forms the source of water for irrigation, drinking and fisheries.

METHODS AND MATERIAL

Study Area

Present work has been conducted in Sarala sagar reservoir situated in Wanaparthy district, Telangana state, India, which is end owed with wide range of littoral and limonitic habitats. Wanaparthy is the one of district in Telangana and is situated between 16^o46'N'-18^o20'N latitudes and 77^o30'-79^o56'E longitudes. Climatically this district fall sunder the tropical region with cyclic rains and has varied habit at Slike Rivers, streams, backwaters, major, medium and minor irrigation tanks. Most of its soils are sandy, sandy loam, lateritic and red soils.

Sarala sagar Reservoir

Saralasar is a medium sized perennial irrigation tank situated at Shankarampeta village, Kothakota mandal [Tehsil] of Wanaparthy district, Telangana state in India. It is constructed across the Chinnavagu, a tributary of Krishna River about 21kms away from the district the ad-quarters and 142kms away from the state capital Hyderabad. It is situated on 16^o46' N latitude and 77^o56' E longitude shown in Figure1. The main purpose of construction of this reservoir was to up lift the economic condition of the natives and to eliminate the scarcity of food grains and water problems in the drought-prone and economically backward villages of the Kothakota mandal. Now Sarala sagar reservoir has become prime importance for irrigation, supplying drinking water to surrounding Villages, Wanaparthy town and also for aquaculture practices. About 176 fisher men families depend on this reservoir in continuing their lives. Thus, this reservoir plays several roles in the rural economy. Sarala sagar reservoir is the first siphon system dam in India as well as in Asia and second in the world. In these reservoir 17 hood siphons, 4 priming siphons were used. Whenever Water level of the tank exceeds its capacity, the siphons System automatically opens.

The water samples from the surface were collected from the three sampling stations every month in polythene cans for a period of 2 years from March 2017 to February 2019. Water samples were collected in separate 250 ml glass bottles (BOD bottles) for the estimation of

dissolved oxygen. All the samples were carried to the laboratory. The samples were analyzed on the same day for different physico-chemical factors following the standard methods,^[8]

One liter of the sample was kept in sedimentation columns after adding 4% formaldehyde solution. The samples were kept in dark undisturbed for about fifteen days for complete settling of the organisms. Finally the sample was concentrated to 100 ml.

Figure 1: Location of Sarala Sagar reservoir in Wanaparthy District, Telangana, India.

Figure 2: A View of Sarala Sagar reservoir.

Water Quality Parameters

The sampling was carried out during morning between 8.00 AM to 9.00 AM. For physico-chemical analysis samples were collected weekly during April 2018 to March 2019. Water samples were collected in 2 litres capacity plastic cans. The water and air temperature were

recorded at the sampling site itself by mercury thermometer. Dissolved oxygen was fixed on the spot itself in BOD bottles. The parameters like free CO₂, alkalinity, total hardness, total dissolved solids, calcium, magnesium, phosphates and chlorides were estimated as per the standard methods.^[9,10]

For the estimation of phytoplankton, the water samples were transferred to cleaned 500 ml polyethylene bottles. Then, 5 ml of lugol's iodine solution and 10-15 ml of 4% formaldehyde were added to it for fixation and preservation of planktonic cells. Planktons were enumerated using Sedge wick Raftar cell^[11] and expressed as numbers per litre. Qualitative identification of phytoplankton organisms was done with the help of monographs and they are identified up to species level.^[12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Water Quality

Seasonal variations in the physico-chemical parameters of water of the present reservoir is summarized in Table 1. Seasonal analysis of water temperature showed that it was highest in summer and relatively lower in monsoon and winter (Table I). The highest rainfall was recorded in the month of August with 23.19cm for the year 2017-18 and there was zero rainfall in the months of December and January for the year 2017-18 and 2018-19 the highest rainfall 34.01cm was recorded in the month of October and nil rainfall was recorded in the month of March 2018-19. pH is considered as important chemical parameter in water body since most of the aquatic organisms are adapted to an average pH and do not withstand abrupt changes. The maximum pH was recorded in summer it may be due to leaching of soil followed by the decomposition of plankton^[20] and minimum in monsoon. The present study shows the acceptable range of pH for fish culture.

Carbonates(CO₃): Showed high values of 28.15 mg/lit in winter season and lower values 20.89 mg/L in rainy season the reason may be the high rain fall in rainy season, the concentration of CO₃ are low where as in winter season it is accumulated for the year 2017-18, for the year 2018-19 the lowest values of concentration of CO₃ 20.89 mg/L was recorded in rainy season but where as in summer and winter the concentration of CO₃ are all most same, the reason may be the rain fall is high 16.02 cm and less temperature 24.7°C for the year 2018-19.

Bicarbonates (HCO₃): High concentrations are recorded in summer season 220.64 mg/L and lower 208.19 mg/L was recorded in rainy season, in winter season the concentration of HCO₃ was 225.59 mg/L is near to summer season for the year 2017-18, for the year 2018-19 the lowest value of HCO₃ recorded 212.64 mg/L in summer season followed by rainy season 208.19 mg/L and highest values were recorded 224.85 in winter season. This may be due to high rain fall 16.02 cm and low temperature 24.2⁰c in winter season in summer season the rainfall was 2.10 cm it may be the root cause for the less concentration of HCO₃.

Chloride (Cl): Highest values of chlorides were recorded in the month of summer for the both years 30.03 mg/L and lowest was recorded in rainy season 20.20 mg/L and 20.20 mg/L for both the years.

Dissolved oxygen (DO): The lowest values were recorded 8.60 and 8.73 mg/L in summer season for both years 2017-18 and 2018-19 the winter season shows high concentration of dissolved oxygen 10.52 and 9.46 mg/L for the study period (2017-19), this may be due to low temperatures.

Sulphates (SO₄): Showed high values of 61.56 mg/L in summer season and lower values 12.93 mg/L in rainy season the reason may be the high rain fall in rainy season, the concentration of SO₄ are low where as in summer season it is accumulated for the year 2017-18, for the year 2018-19 the lowest values of concentration of SO₄ 12.93 mg/L was recorded in rainy season but where as in summer and winter the concentration of SO₄ are all most same, the reason may be the rain fall is high 16.02 cm and less temperature 24.8⁰c.

Fluorides (F): High concentrations are recorded in both summer seasons 1.03 mg/l and 1.08 mg/L (2017-18). Lowest value was recorded in rainy season 053 mg/L and 0.52 mg/L in both years (2017-19). Moderate values are recorded in winter seasons 0.63 mg/L and 0.61 mg/L for the both years of 2017-2019.

Magnesium (Mg): Highest values of Magnesium were recorded in the winter season for the both the years 24.66 mg/L and lowest value was recorded in rainy season 19.14 mg/L and 19.14 mg/L for both the years.

Calcium (Ca): The lowest values of calcium were recorded 27.27 and 28.85 mg/L in winter season for both years 2017-18 and 2018-19 the summer season shows high concentration of

Calcium values 29.29 and 29.09 mg/L for the study period (2017-19), this may be due to low temperatures.

Potassium (K): Highest values of K were recorded in the summer season 4.86 mg/L, in rainy and winter seasons 4.5 and 4.63 mg/L in year of 2017-2018. Whereas in rainy and winter seasons recorded 4.99 mg/L and 4.99 mg/lit, summer season having 4.83.mg/L.

Nitrate (NO₃): Both the years summer season recorded lowest values 2.7mg/L in 2017-18, 2.19 mg/L in 2018-19, highest values are recorded for the both years of 2017-18 and 2018-2019 the values are 3.2 mg/L and 3.66 mg/L. Moderate values are recorded both the years of winter season The maximum temperatures were recorded in the summer season for the both years with 34.11°C and rainy season it was 24.65°C for the year (2017-18) 21.8 summer (2018-19) and rainfall 26.7 (2018-19) and the minimum rainfall was recorded in the rainy season with 1.56cm for the year 2017-18 and it was 21.45cm maximum rainfall for the year 2018-19.

Phytoplankton

The maximum no of Chlorophyceae members were seen in rainy season 157.16 and 121.9 no of organisms/milt seen for the both years 2017-18, 2018-19 respectively and minimum was recorded in the summer season with 125.4 and 89.78 no of organisms /milt for the years 2017-18 and 2018-19 respectively and shows an average of 141.16 and 111.13 no of organisms/milt for the both years 2017-18 and 2018-19. Whereas Cyanophyceae members were dominating in summer season 132.33 and 160.75 for the years 2017-18 and 2018-19 respectively.

Whereas in the rainy and winter seasons showing the nearest reading 118 and 117.33 no of organisms/milt, this may be due to the temperatures 26.3 and 24.65°C for the year 2018-19 it was all together a different it shows the temperature was 26.01 in rainy season with 124.08 no of organisms/milt and in winter season 24.9°C that shows the temperature with almost 2°C different the no of organisms Cyanophyceae members were reduced with 103.48 no of organisms/milt as a temperature was decreasing summer to winter season the no of organisms Cyanophyceae members showing a decline condition.

Coming to the Bacillariophyceae members high number was recorded in winter season 109.66 and 112.83 numbers for the years 2017-18 and 2018-19 respectively. For the year 2017-18 the Bacillariophyceae members maintained all most the same reading 100.06 and 101.83 no of organisms/milt in summer and rainy seasons this may be due to the temperatures are with only 5°c different and the rainfall was 13cm different. For the year 2018-19 the minimum no of organisms of Bacillariophyceae members 97 no of organisms/milt were recorded in the rainy season this may be due to high rainfall 21.45cm and temperature was 26.2°c, in summer season the number is 120.5 no of organisms/milt this may be due to the rainfall 4.13cm and high temperature 21.8°c and the no of organisms/milt 120.5.

Table I: Shows average values of stations season wise for two years.

S. No	Year	Season	Tempoc	Rainfall cm	pH	CO ₃ mg/L	HCO ₃ mg/L	CL mg/L	DO mg/L	SO ₄ mg/L	F mg/L	Mg mg/L	Ca mg/L	K mg/L	NO ₃ mg/L
1	2017-18	Summer	33.3	2.78	8.17	22.84	220.64	30.03	8.60	61.56	74.10	21.45	29.29	4.8	2.77
2	2017-18	Rainy	26.42	16.02	8.22	20.89	208.19	20.20	8.14	12.93	69.63	19.14	28.63	4.5	3.21
3	2017-18	Winter	24.8	1.77	8.18	28.15	225.59	22.49	10.52	49.51	75.34	24.66	27.27	4.63	2.99
4	2018-19	Summer	33.02	3.38	8.23	24.63	212.64	30.03	8.73	61.81	74.11	21.62	29.04	4.8	2.10
5	2018-19	Rainy	26.42	16.02	8.22	20.89	208.19	20.20	8.14	12.93	69.63	19.14	28.63	4.99	3.66
6	2018-19	Winter	24.65	2.97	8.13	29.06	224.85	21.98	9.46	49.75	76.01	23.57	28.85	4.99	2.44

Table II: Shows season wise cumulative algal diversity in the two years at stations.

S. No	Years	Season	Temp O _C	Rainfall cm	Chlorophyceae no of organisms/ ml	Cyanophyceae no of organisms/ ml	Bacillariophyceae no of organisms/ ml
1	Year I	Summer	34.1	1.56	125.4	132.33	100.06
2	Year I	Rainy	26.3	1.56	157.16	118	101.83
3	Year I	Winter	24.65	1.37	141.16	117.33	109.66
4	Year II	Summer	21.8	4.13	89.78	160.75	120.5
5	Year II	Rainy	26.2	21.45	121.9	103.48	97
6	Year II	Winter	24.9	1.5	111.13	87.5	112.83

Table-III, IV and V. Algal members which were identified in Sarala sagar Reservoir.

Table-III.

S. No	CYANOPHYCEAE
1	<i>Anabaena iyengar</i>
2	<i>Anabaena variabilis</i>
3	<i>Chroococcus minutus</i>
4	<i>Calothrix membranaceae</i>
5	<i>Gloeocapsa atrata</i>
6	<i>Gloeotrichia pisum</i>
7	<i>Gloeotrichia natans</i>
8	<i>Hydrococcus sps</i>
9	<i>Merismopedia glauca</i>
10	<i>Nostoc sps</i>
11	<i>Nostoc linchia</i>
12	<i>Oscillatoria limposa</i>
13	<i>Oscillatoria formosa</i>
14	<i>Oscillatoria tenuis</i>
15	<i>Phormidium sps</i>
16	<i>Phormidiummucosum</i>
17	<i>Phormidiummolle</i>
18	<i>Rivularia sps</i>
19	<i>Spirulina sps</i>
20	<i>Synechococcus sps</i>
21	<i>Triconema sps</i>

Table-IV.

Sl. No	BACILLARIO PHYCEAE
1	<i>Amphora ovalis</i>
2	<i>Cymbella sps</i>
3	<i>Cymbellaaffinis</i>
4	<i>Cymbella sturbegidula</i>
5	<i>Diatoma sps</i>
6	<i>Fragilaria crotonensis</i>
7	<i>Frustulia sps</i>
8	<i>Gamphonima gracile</i>
9	<i>Navicula radiosa</i>
10	<i>Navicula cryptocephala</i>
11	<i>Nitzschia sps</i>
12	<i>Pinnularia biceps</i>
13	<i>Synedra sps</i>
14	<i>Synedra ulna</i>
15	<i>Pinnularia viridis</i>

Table-V.

S.No	CHLOROPHYCEAE
1	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>
2	<i>Clamydomonas sps</i>
3	<i>Chara vulgaris</i>
4	<i>Cladophora glomarata</i>
5	<i>Cladophora crispate</i>
6	<i>Cosmarium leave</i>
7	<i>Cosmarium granatum</i>
8	<i>Cosmarium javanicum</i>
9	<i>Coelastrum combaricum</i>
10	<i>Closterium porrectum</i>
11	<i>Hydrodictyon reticulatum</i>
12	<i>Nitella sps</i>
13	<i>Oocystis gigas</i>
14	<i>Pediastrum duplex</i>
15	<i>Pediastrum simplex</i>
16	<i>Pandorina sps</i>
17	<i>Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum</i>
18	<i>Radiococcus nimbatus</i>
19	<i>Scenedesmus armatus</i>
20	<i>Scenedesmus denticulatus</i>
21	<i>Scenedesmus dimorphus</i>
22	<i>Stigeoclonium tenue</i>
23	<i>Stigeoclonium pinnatum</i>
24	<i>Stigeoclonium sps</i>
25	<i>Spirogyra indica</i>
26	<i>Spirogyra sps</i>
27	<i>Tetraedron gracile</i>
28	<i>Ulothrix sps</i>
29	<i>Volvox sps</i>
30	<i>Zygnemac zurde</i>

CONCLUSION

Planktons are important food sources of fishes specially the commercially culturing fish species. The present study shows the rich in phyto plankton diversity they are chlorococcales, diatoms, desmids, euglenoids and blue- greens. The commercially culturing fishes are almost clearly indicates the unpolluted condition of the wetland^[21,22] reported that, in Kithamlake, Agra, euglenoids density was maximum during summer followed by rainy and minimum during winter months. Euglenoids occur in greater number in polluted water bodies^[23] have recorded maximum euglenoids during monsoon and low during post-monsoon. In the present study, Zygnemophyceae is dominant followed by Chlorophyceae. phytoplankton feeders. So the lake is suitable for fish culture. Based on the present

investigations the water is soft water, it is dominating phytoplankton diversity.

Sarala sagar Reservoir harboured 66 species belonging to 45 genera is rich in phytoplankton diversity and hence productive. Based on the data on physico-chemical parameters in relation to phytoplankton distribution and abundance forms a useful tool for further ecological assessment and monitoring of water bodies. They are the risk of pollution by human anthropogenic and agricultural activities. It is suggested that continuous assessing of water body and make a plan to protect it from pollution.

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